

Smarandache-Rodrigues-Maiorino (SRM) Theory

by

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Studying solutions of Maxwell and Dirac-Weyl equations, Waldyr Rodrigues Jr. and José Maiorino were able to propose a full-unified theory for constructing of arbitrary speeds in nature (for arbitrary they meant $0 \leq v < \text{infinity}$) in 1996 [3]. So that Smarandache Hypothesis proposed in 1972 [6, 2], that there is no speed barrier in the universe, can be promoted to theory, as Smarandache-Rodrigues-Maiorino (SRM) theory [2, 1].

What is unique about Rodrigues-Maiorino theory is that special relativity principle suffers a breakdown, however, even relativistic constructions of quantum mechanics, such as Dirac equation, agree completely with superluminal phenomena. Also, according to Rodrigues-Maiorino theory, even well positioned mirrors can accelerate an electromagnetic wave to velocities greater of the light. This assumption was later on confirmed by Saari and Reivelt in 1997 [4], who produced a X-wave (named this way by J. Y. Lu, a Rodrigues' contributor [5]) using a xenon lamp intercepted with a set of lens and orifices.

The SRM theory is a mathematical pure and strong solution of the relativistic quantum wave equation, indicating that there is no speed limit in the universe, and therefore is the most powerful theory today for construction of arbitrary speeds.

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